

**JUST
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4 ALL**

T3.2 NORTH-CENTRAL PORTUGAL REGIONAL REPORT

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DISCLAIMER AND FORWARD

This case study about wind energy developments in the north-central region of Portugal has been produced for the Horizon Europe JustWind4All project as part of WP3 task 3.2. The task aims to develop an understanding of regional challenges and opportunities around wind energy governance over the past 5-10 years to formulate key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is based on a mixed method approach including for each region: document reviews (around 50), 5-10 interviews with wind energy governance actors and a media and policy analysis. A comparative analysis across cases and across the project's regions allows for a better understanding of challenges and opportunities around effective and just wind energy governance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 COUNTRY CONTEXT

1.1.1. ENERGY SYSTEM

Portugal, situated on the western coast of the Iberian Peninsula, is a small country lacking domestic reserves of coal, gas, or oil. Consequently, the nation has historically relied on the importation of non-renewable primary sources of energy. Prior to 1995, Portugal's energy landscape was predominantly shaped by oil, constituting approximately 60% of the national energy production (Observatório da Energia et al. 2023). In the realm of renewable energy, significant contributions have been made by large hydropower projects, generating an annual production ranging from 6 to 14 GW (DGEG 2023). However, the growth potential of hydropower was constrained by the limited availability of suitable locations and the challenges associated with constructing new large dams (Bento and Fontes 2015).

In the 21st century, Portugal made remarkable strides to transform its energy landscape, reducing its reliance on fossil fuels through strategic and aggressive policies. The government, cognisant of the need for sustainable energy sources, implemented a series of policies emphasising the development of wind and solar energy (Delicado et al. 2015). They were a response to the Directive 28/2009/CE of the European Parliament and the Council, which compelled member states to devise plans aimed at escalating their renewable energy production. In 2010, Portugal unveiled its National Action Plan for Renewable Energy (PNAER, Plano Nacional de Ação para as Energias Renováveis), committing to achieving a 31% share of renewable energy in primary energy consumption by 2020. Remarkably, Portugal surpassed this target, reaching a significant milestone of 34.0% in 2020.

In compliance with Regulation (EU) 2018/1999, the European Union mandated member states to formulate comprehensive action plans aligning energy and climate objectives with the binding EU targets for the period 2021–2030. Portugal responded by approving the National Energy and Climate Plan 2030 (PNEC 2030, Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima) in 2020 (RCM n.º 53/2020, of July 10 2020). This action plan sets an ambitious goal for Portugal to increase the share of renewable energy in its total consumption to 47%.

The focus on renewable energy not only transformed Portugal's energy landscape but also had a positive impact on various decarbonization indicators (Observatório da Energia et al. 2023):

- Energy dependence decreased from 79.4% in 2011 to 67.1% in 2021.
- Energy exports increased significantly, rising from 3,546 (2011) to 5,811 (2021).
- Fossil fuel emissions resulting from energy production dropped substantially, decreasing from 48.2 Mt CO₂e in 2011 to 37.0 Mt CO₂e.

An internationally recognized milestone was achieved in 2021 when Portugal shut down its last two coal thermoelectric plants. This decision led to a drastic reduction in coal imports, plummeting from 5,035,000 tons in 2011 to a mere 9,000 tons in 2021.

Despite notable progress in diversifying its energy sources, Portugal remains reliant on oil imports, experiencing a modest reduction in its share of final consumption from 50.5% in 2011 to 44.4% in 2021 (Figure 1). In line with the REPowerEU plan's introduction and the broader goal of enhancing the national renewable energy output, the government is now actively seeking to bolster investments in solar and offshore wind energy.

Figure 1. Evolution of the total consumption of primary energy. Adapted from Observatório de Energia et al. (2023). Source: DGEG

1.1.2. WIND ENERGY

Wind energy has emerged as a pivotal renewable energy source in Portugal, undergoing significant growth and securing its position as a leading component of the country’s renewable energy portfolio, closely following hydropower. Portugal started discussing wind energy after the oil crisis in the 70s, but it was only in the 80s when exploratory activities in wind technologies took place. The first wind power plant (WPP) was established in 1986 in the island of Porto Santo, Madeira, and the first mainland WPP was established in 1990 in Sines (INEGI and APREN 2023). Subsequently, the sector experienced steady progress, marked by a consistent growth rate of approximately 40% annually. This growth trajectory reached its zenith between 2004–2006, witnessing a remarkable increase of over 60% of installed capacity each year (Figure 1). This surge was attributed to a series of incentives introduced by the government in 2001, designed to encourage substantial investments in wind energy projects (Figure 2), a topic that will be explored in detail in subsequent sections.

Following this period of rapid expansion, the pace of wind energy development decelerated significantly after 2012, with a growth rate of less than 6% per year (INEGI and APREN 2023) (Figure 2). Several factors contributed to this slowdown, notably the change in governing parties in 2011 and the profound economic crisis that affected Europe in 2008.

Figure 2. Cumulative installed capacity of wind power in Portugal. Source: e2p (2023)

Despite this deceleration, the share of wind energy in Portugal's overall energy consumption showcased an impressive upward trajectory. Starting from a modest 5.9% in 2006, it surged to a remarkable 23.9% in 2023 (Figure 3). This achievement culminated in a significant milestone for Portugal in 2021, where annual renewable energy consumption constituted a notable 34.0% of the country's total energy consumption (Observatório da Energia et al. 2023).

Fonte | Source: [REN datahub](https://datahub.ren.pt/)

Figure 3. Wind generation vs. electricity demand in mainland Portugal. Source: e2p (2023)

Facing the challenge of limited available land for wind energy projects, the Portuguese government shifted its focus to the country's extensive coastline in 2021, aiming to harness the potential of offshore wind energy. In this endeavour, Portugal was the first European country to deploy floating offshore wind turbines. EDP Renewables, a key player in the renewable energy sector, spearheaded this innovative approach by constructing and managing a prototype WPP named WindFloat. Situated in Viana do Castelo, the plant comprised three floating platforms, each equipped with a wind turbine boasting a capacity of 8.4 MW (EDP 2020). The first turbine commenced operations in December 2019, followed by the remaining two turbines in May 2020. This achievement not only demonstrated the feasibility of floating offshore wind technology but also paved the way for future investments in large-scale commercial offshore floating WPPs.

Geographically, WPPs in Portugal are predominantly situated in coastal regions and mountainous areas, aligning with regions where winds are more frequent. However, due to the high population density along the Portuguese coast, WPPs have primarily been established inland, specifically on mountains, to harness the country's wind resources to their fullest extent (Figure 3). There are a few exceptions, notably in the eastern regions of the country, near the border with Spain, where relatively few WPPs are located.

In the Azores, wind energy production experienced a doubling in output around 2009, followed by another surge in 2012. Afterwards, wind capacity remained relatively stable. Presently, the 55 turbines in the Azores collectively generate 36.7 MW, constituting approximately 10% of the island's energy share. On the other hand, Madeira witnessed an exponential growth in wind energy between 2009 and 2012. While both the Azores and Madeira demonstrated stability in wind energy production after 2012, Madeira experienced an additional growth phase in 2021, resulting in a 1.5-fold increase in energy production. Currently, Madeira hosts 64 active turbines, totaling 64.2 MW of installed capacity (INEGI and APREN 2023).

Figure 4. Installed capacity per district and autonomous region in 2022. Source: e2p

1.2 REGIONAL CONTEXT

The north-central region of Portugal (hereafter abbreviated as NCRP) covers the NUTS II regions PT11 and PT16, and the districts of Viana do Castelo, Braga, Vila Real, Bragança, Porto, Aveiro, Viseu, Guarda, Coimbra, Castelo Branco and Leiria (Figure 4).

Figure 5. NUTS II regions in Portugal. Source: Wikipedia CC BY-SA 4.0

The North-Central Region of Portugal (NCRP) is notable for its dense concentration of wind power plants. In contrast to the predominantly flat terrain in the south, except for the coastal regions, the NCRP is characterised by intricate mountain ranges with diverse wind patterns. These mountains exhibit a low population density, unlike the densely inhabited southwestern coastal areas. The unique topography of the NCRP offers opportunities for the installation of WPPs in complex orographic regions with substantial wind potential (Figure 5). Importantly, these areas are often situated far from local populations, making the NCRP an appealing region for project developers.

However, the same mountainous landscapes that offer promising wind energy prospects also possess significant natural and cultural heritage value. These regions boast extensive coverage of protected areas where the development of WPPs is, or should be, restricted. The NCRP attracts nearly two million visitors annually, drawn by its rich heritage (INE 2023). This influx of tourists has occasionally sparked conflicts between project developers and stakeholders committed to preserving these culturally and ecologically significant areas. The ensuing tensions and conflicts will be explored in detail in the subsequent sections.

Figure 6. Map of the onshore wind potential in mainland Portugal. Source: LNEG (revised in 2022 Jun 8)

Among the five planned offshore areas, three are on the coast of the NCRP: Viana do Castelo, Leixões, and Figueira da Foz. These areas collectively represent a substantial installed capacity of 10 GW, with 7.5 GW concentrated within these three locations. This notable investment has sparked concerns among the local fishing communities, who worry about the potential negative impact on their commercial activities. Additionally, environmentalists have expressed fears about certain designated areas overlapping with protected regions, raising ecological concerns about these developments.

In summary, the NCRP serves as a battleground for the conflicts between landscape preservation and technological advancements caused by wind energy deployment. These conflicts manifest both inland, where historical sites are at risk, and at sea, where offshore wind energy projects are in progress.

It's crucial to emphasise that, in terms of historical development, key actors, legal frameworks, narrative shifts, and cultural values, there is not a clear-cut regional demarcation. This observation was consistently supported during our interviews. Therefore, we will specifically mention the NCRP in cases where distinct differences are notable and use the broader term "Portugal" elsewhere in the report.

1.3 AIMS AND REPORT STRUCTURE

This case study traces the development of wind energy governance in the NCRP over a time span of nearly 40 years. It thus zooms in on how to participate in social actions and processes for or against

wind energy, and outlines how these actions and processes are co-shaped by regulations, discourses and norms over time. Doing so allows to highlight regional challenges and opportunities of wind energy governance. This report is one out of a set of seven case study reports that together will provide insights for the formulation of key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is in this way that it connects to JustWind4All's ambition of understanding how wind energy governance can become more just and effective.

Specifically, this report provides a historical understanding of the interplay between diverse types of actors around wind energy development in the NCRP. At the heart of this report is an overview of the historical narrative of how wind energy governance developed in Portugal along four phases: formation, implementation and growth, stagnation, and offshore wind and repowering – see Section 4. Each of these phases is connected to at least one critical instance of change, i.e. a point in time that was critical for the development of wind energy in Portugal, i.e. new legislation that boosted wind energy development (critical instance 1); a change in governing parties (critical instance 2); and new European legislation to accelerate renewable energy development (critical instance 3). The historical narrative is followed by an 'Analysis and Discussion' section (Section 5) along the following analytical questions:

1. which governance arrangements and processes are in place; that is, what was the ensemble of actors (human and non-human) that come together in the intentional coordination of social action around wind energy (for and against wind energy);
2. which regulatory, normative and cultural-cognitive institutions are co-shaping social activities around wind energy (these can derive from EU, national, regional and local, for instance, planning processes and landscape governance);
3. which participatory practices are being discussed and/or practised (or not) over time and how are they being perceived and implemented by diverse wind actors;
4. and how are notions of energy justice and energy sovereignty being discussed, narrated and practised (or not) over time? How do they relate to changing governance arrangements and processes?

While Section 2 provides a succinct overview of the main insights of the analysis and historical narrative, Section 6 provides implications and recommendations for fostering just and effective wind energy governance in the region and beyond. For an overview of the methodology underlying this report, please see Section 3.

2 KEY INSIGHTS

- Citizen participation in wind energy projects is slowly catching up with the levels observed in other European countries. The development of wind energy between 2001—2010 was too fast and people were not yet aware of the consequences brought by wind parks to local communities. But in recent years perceptions have changed, and new wind parks are seeing more backlash from local communities. For example, the innovative and ambitious goal of the government to build 10 GW of offshore wind energy has been facing resistance from fishers and environmental organisations.
- No attempts have yet been made by developers to involve local communities in project planning. Therefore, the benefits of this approach in democratising participation, increasing (the feeling of) community ownership and decreasing project resistance can only be speculated.
- The introduction of a 2.5% rent on wind power plant profits under Decree-Law 339-C/2001, of December 29, helped to increase acceptance by municipalities to wind energy projects. But it is unclear how this income was used to benefit local communities.
- New developments on wind energy will be focused on repowering onshore wind power plants and constructing new offshore wind power plants. Both provide opportunities to create social innovations on public participation regarding wind energy, something that has lacked so far in the NCRP.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

JustWind4All makes use of a historical and embedded case study approach. The project's main interest is to understand how wind energy governance can become more just and effective. To this end it develops historical case studies that allow to trace the development of wind energy governance in European regions over the time span of 5-10 years. In the case studies, we focus on wind energy governance arrangements and processes and how these are co-shaped by regulations, discourses, and norms. With governance, we refer to the interplay between diverse types of actors (i.e. arrangements) that participate in the intentional coordination of social actions (i.e. processes) connected to wind energy. These can be social actions for and against wind energy.

We carried out document reviews and interviews between April 2023 and September 2023 to collect information, which are detailed next.

3.1.1 DOCUMENT REVIEW

To answer the questions outlined in section 1.3, we executed a scoping review for relevant documents using the following keywords in both English (en-UK) and Portuguese (pt-PT) when applicable: 'wind energy', 'wind (park OR farm OR plant)', 'participation OR engagement', 'governance', 'Portugal'. We reviewed the abstracts and headlines of documents identified in our initial search and analysed full documents when these sections were deemed pertinent to the objectives of this report. Additionally, we enhanced our research by exploring forward links and backlinks referenced in those documents thereby gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the events mentioned.

We conducted searches and examined the databases of Google Scholar and Semantic Scholar to identify primary sources of information such as scientific articles, books and theses. This search yielded a total of 12 scientific articles, two books and six theses.

Additionally, we covered TV broadcasts on popular national channels such as RTP and SIC, and newspaper articles about wind energy in national newspapers (PÚBLICO, Expresso, TSF, etc.) and smaller or local newspapers focused on the NCRP (Notícias do Nordeste, etc.). These sources proved to be excellent for obtaining local and specialised information that may not be readily available through other channels. This search yielded a total of 18 newspaper articles and four TV broadcasts.

Furthermore, we searched actors' websites for reports, blog posts and press releases referencing wind energy. These are an excellent source to understand actors' aims and values, and how they frame wind energy accordingly. Actors considered included citizen groups, environmental non-governmental organisations, researchers and their institutions, public institutions, and project developers. This search yielded a total of five reports and two blog posts.

Finally, we scoured the Diário da República and the European Union website for legislation that referenced wind energy. This search was often made following the previous sources when they referenced a decree-law or council resolution rather than a direct consultation. This search yielded a total of 16 statutes.

3.1.2 INTERVIEWS AND EVENTS

We used an interview guide for all regional case studies to conduct interviews. The interview guide, participant information and ethical consent form were translated for the in-depth interviews. Interview questions were formulated based on a background check on the affiliation of the interviewee, as well as knowledge gaps that were raised during the document review. Questions were deliberately broad to elicit information about actors, narratives, relevant legislation and issues of justice, and differed slightly due to the different role, position and background of the interviewees. Other differences could be found in terms of the overall time spent with the interviewees, the amount of time spent on each theme, as well as the use of open questions that arose during the interview. Interviews lasted an average of one hour (range 43—97 minutes, see Annex 2) and were conducted by the same member of the FCiências.ID team.

Interviewees were selected based on their roles in and their involvement with wind energy in the NCRP, as well as through referrals from other interviewees. In total, we interviewed nine individuals, with two of them participating in a joint interview together (resulting in eight separate interviews). Among these individuals, three were affiliated with an environmental non-governmental organisation (ENGO), two were researchers, two were associated with the Portuguese Renewable Energy Association (APREN), one represented an energy cooperative (Coopérnico), and one was from a developer company (EDP Renewables) (see Annex 2). We attempted to contact six additional entities for interviews (STRIX, Finerge, Ventient Energy, GENERG, REN, and a researcher from NOVA FCSH), but they either did not respond or were unavailable at the time.

All interviews were recorded with the consent of interviewees and transcribed nearly integrally, with the help of Microsoft Office transcriber. Interviewees were informed that the collected data would be treated confidentially and they would be quoted anonymously in the case study report. After having written a first full version of this report, we checked with every interviewee how they would like to be referenced in the report (organisation's name, anonymously, etc.), whether we could use their direct quotes (providing an opportunity to edit the quotes) and whether there is anything they would like to share after having read the report.

Results of the work done in this report were shared in two academic meetings. We took notes and talked with some participants, but ultimately the discussed themes were not relevant for this report.

3.2 EMPIRICAL REFLECTIONS

We did not find many sources mentioning public participation in wind energy. This was expected according to the feedback we obtained from interviews. However, it does not discard the possibility that public participation could occur at a more local level, where it is less noticeable.

We got a higher success rate of interview acceptance for interviewees which are typically associated with opposition to wind energy (e.g. ENGOs) than for interviewees that support wind energy. The ENGOs that we contacted, as well as Coopérnico and APREN, all answered positively to our interview request. Two of our first contacted researchers were too busy at the time, but we successfully interviewed another two researchers. Project developers were the hardest to successfully accept our invitation for an interview, a trend shared by other members of the JustWind4All project consortium. We had to put a larger effort in investigating their opinions and beliefs because of this. This means there is the possibility of bias in our description of project developers' opinions, values and beliefs that we acknowledge here.

We asked broad questions to interviewees to elicit general responses. While broad, some questions were made with their affiliation in mind, and thus were more targeted than others. This means that responses were not standardised throughout the interviews. Interviews were not standardised between interviewees, and perspectives in favour or against wind energy might not be balanced. The same thing occurred with our literature review. Resistance towards wind energy is more noticed in the press, while support for wind energy was mostly restricted to companies' websites, which biases the comparison of different perspectives. Therefore, when reading the report, it is important to acknowledge that missing or biased information does not reflect the authors' views on the subject, but rather limitations into how information was collected.

4 WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN NORTH-CENTRAL REGION OF PORTUGAL

4.1 PRE-PERIOD: PHASE OF FORMATION (1985–2000)

Before wind energy gained prominence in Portugal, renewable energy production was dominated by large hydropower (>10 MW). It accounted for 86% renewable energy share in 1995, particularly in the NCRP region, where the largest reservoirs were situated. In 1988, the landscape shifted with the enactment of Decree-Law n.º 188/88, of May 27 (1988), which permitted private companies to engage in energy production from small hydropower (<10 MW). However, this change did not lead to a significant increase in the installed power (246 MW in 1995 vs. 307 MW in 2004). Additionally, hydropower had a limited growth potential due to the scarcity of available area and the challenges associated with constructing new large dams (Bento and Fontes 2015a).

Amidst the oil shock in the 1980s, Portugal initiated research and development (R&D) on renewable energy technologies. National laboratories sought European research funds and collaborated with international consortiums to start exploring wind technology and potential (Bento and Fontes 2015b). The first experimental wind turbine, a German two-blade AEROMAN 12/20, was installed near Sintra in 1985 by LNETI, the National Laboratory for Engineering and Industrial Technology (actual LNEG, National Laboratory of Energy and Geology), and represented the cutting edge of wind energy technology at the time (Estanqueiro and Jesus 1996; Interviewee 6 2023). LNEG, and other research groups such as the Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering (INEGI, Instituto de Ciência e Inovação em Engenharia Mecânica) played pivotal roles in the initial phase of wind development. Their participation was instrumental in establishing a local knowledge base on wind modelling and evaluation, proving valuable later when the market experienced significant growth. LNEG conducted a comprehensive study of Portugal's wind resources, and used this data to create a wind resource database, EOLOS, in 2000. Subsequently, the first Wind Power Atlas was published in 2004. The release of EOLOS and the wind atlas spurred a surge in new energy projects from 2000 onwards, as companies leveraged this data to optimise the locations of wind energy projects (interviewee 6).

The first WPPs were installed, surprisingly not in mainland Portugal, but in the islands of Porto Santo (Madeira, 1985) and Santa Maria (Azores, 1988), both featuring AEROMAN turbines. The power plants were established under the VALOREN program (Council Regulation (EEC) No 3301/86 of 27 October 1986), arguably the first policy breakthrough regarding wind energy implementation in Portugal. The program aimed to enhance the capacity of disadvantaged member states to produce endogenous energy. Financial support was granted by means of a non-refundable subsidy covering up to 70% of the investment. The Secretary of State for Energy at the time took a substantial interest in the program and supported the electricity companies of Azores (EDA – Eletricidade dos Açores) and Madeira (EM – Eletricidade da Madeira) in allocating part of the budget to construct the first WPPs on their respective islands (Delicado et al. 2015). In fact, some policies (e.g. Decree-Law n.º 189/88) were initially framed within the VALOREN program.

The formative phase marked the birth of the Portuguese Renewable Energy Association, APREN (Associação Portuguesa de Energias Renováveis), another key actor in the wind energy sector. APREN emerged following Decree-Law n.º 188/88. According to interviewee 4, APREN's initial framework was focused on hydropower alone because it held the largest share of the renewable energy sector. Sometime later, there was a call to split APREN into different associations, each representing a

renewable energy sector (hydropower, wind, solar, biomass, etc.). The president at the time, observing similar associations being formed in Europe, opposed the move. He argued that, given Portugal's size relative to other countries in the European Union, each sector would have limited lobbying power. Moreover, the government and companies might manipulate each sector to compete with one another, rather than collaborating on what is best for the country (interviewee 4). The president contended that it was crucial to develop the renewable energy sector comprehensively. If each sector was individually represented, they might prioritise their expansion goals to increase influence, rather than taking a holistic approach to the development of renewable energy. Holding closed-doors meetings between developers and investors, and then speaking as an association in unison, would be more effective than public conflicts that attract negative attention from the press. The president at the time succeeded in maintaining APREN as an association that represents all renewable energy sectors. After the president retired in 2015, APREN's mission has remained the same: to bridge the interests of renewable energy companies with the climate and decarbonisation goals imposed by public institutions (Interviewee 4 2023).

The first mainland WPP was installed in Sines in 1992, an achievement that garnered national attention and was featured in the news (*Inauguração de estação de energia eólica 1992*). The second mainland wind park, and the first in the NCRP, was installed four years later (1996) in Viseu, boasting a larger scale with 17 turbines and a capacity of 600 kW. By the year 2000, Portugal had 22 wind parks, three in Azores, seven in Madeira, and seven in the NCRP (INEGI and APREN 2023).

Several new companies were created at this time to explore the country's wind energy potential and develop wind energy technology. For example, the wind energy development company Enernova was created as a subsidiary of the largest energy company at the time, Electricidade de Portugal (EDP).

The first national feed-in tariff, implemented through Decree-Law n.º 189/88, of May 27 (1988), marked one of Europe's early instances of this financial mechanism and established a fixed rate of €0.047/kWh for wind energy over an eight-year period (Bento and Fontes 2015a). The policy was conceived to foster endogenous energy production by independent producers and divert investments from the more competitively priced fossil fuel generated energy. However, the policy yielded limited impact in accelerating wind development: only six WPPs were installed by 1995, cumulatively providing a capacity of 16 MW (Delicado et al. 2015). The first revision to the feed-in tariff occurred through Decree-Law n.º 313/95, of November 24 (1995). The updated formula removed the previous 10 MW cap on installed capacity and concurrently outlined the national energy strategy spanning the period 1995–2015 (Delicado et al. 2015). Subsequently, a comprehensive overhaul in 1999 (Decree-Law n.º 168/99, of May 18 1999) introduced a novel formula incorporating the following considerations: avoided costs of investing in conventional power plants; avoided costs of operating and maintaining such facilities; avoided environmental costs linked to CO₂ emissions; and the inflation rate (Bento and Fontes 2015a; Cardoso 2021). While the feed-in tariff has undergone subsequent revisions, as will be seen later in this report, the fundamental principle of compensating for avoided costs has persisted.

Decree-Law n.º 189/88 also marked the first policy that ensured access to the grid for Independent Power Producers (IPPs) interested in producing renewable energy. Initially confined to small hydropower (<10 MW), an amendment (Decree-Law n.º 313/95, of November 24, 1995) expanded its framework to encompass other renewable energy sources, such as wind power. Opening the possibility of private companies to pursue investments in renewable energy generation was a key change in accelerating the development of wind energy (interviewee 4). Subsequently, the scheme has undergone multiple revisions, reflecting the dynamic evolution of the electricity market and its liberalisation.

The experimentation with small turbines yielded applied knowledge that was used to enhance the efficient implementation of more ambitious WPPs. The positive outcomes from these initial trials not only bolstered the credibility of wind energy as a viable alternative to hydropower for renewable energy production, but also fostered the formation of a respected community of actors within the sector, such as LNEG and APREN. This community, through its collective expertise, significantly contributed to legitimising wind power and disseminating its potential for further growth (Bento and Fontes 2015b). Moreover, the implementation of WPPs unfolded with remarkable self-sufficiency, nearly eliminating the need to enlist international consultants thanks to the substantial technological learning and development achieved by national actors in the field (Bento and Fontes 2015b).

4.2 PRE-PERIOD: PHASE OF GROWTH AND IMPLEMENTATION (2001–2011)

Following a period of scaling up, which spanned roughly from the introduction of the first 500 kW turbines in 1996 to the deployment of 3 MW turbines in 2003, Portugal's wind energy sector entered a phase of substantial growth. This upscaling was propelled by the enactment of incentive policies and the creation of a public tender designed to allocate connection rights.

4.2.1 ENERGY TARGETS

The implementation and growth phase of wind energy in Portugal commenced in 2001, marked by the introduction of significant policies that signalled a substantial commitment to advance wind energy infrastructure. A pivotal development in this trajectory was the publication of Directive 2001/77/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, of September 27 (2001), which promoted “an increase in the contribution of renewable energy sources to electricity production in the internal market for electricity”. Portugal rectified this directive and set a target to reach 3750 MW of wind capacity by 2010 (RCM n.º 63/2003, of April 28 2003). Portugal ended up surpassing this goal, reaching 3937 MW by 2010.

In alignment with the European Directive on renewable electricity, the Portuguese government launched the E4 Program (Energy Efficiency and Endogenous Energies, RCM n.º 154/2001, of October 19 2001), considered to mark the true inception of renewable energy policy in Portugal (Delicado et al. 2015). The E4 Program aimed to enhance access to energy available in the market, improve energy efficiency — especially from the demand side — and value all forms of renewable energy, spanning hydro, wind, biomass, solar (both thermal and photovoltaic), and wave energy. The E4 Program also set an ambitious target set at 39% (later increased to 45%) for the country's gross electricity consumption to be supplied from renewable energy (including large hydropower) by 2010.

In 2005, the newly elected socialist government introduced a comprehensive set of incentives to expedite the development of renewable energy. The new National Energy Strategy (RCM n.º 169/2005, of October 24, 2005) set a more ambitious target for 5.1 GW of wind energy production. It also emphasised increased investments on research to maximise energetic efficiency and reduce CO₂ emissions, including capturing and storing CO₂.

4.2.2 FEED-IN TARIFF

The key legislation that significantly changed the deployment of wind energy in Portugal was Decree-Law n.º 339-C/2001, of December 29 (2001), which changed Decree-Law n.º 189/88, of May 27 (1988).

The feed-in tariff formula was updated, with the introduction of a new factor, to differentiate between renewable technologies. Under the new legislation, €0.082/kWh would be paid for the first 2 000 hours of wind energy production each year. The tariff was reduced by blocks of 200 hours, reaching a minimum of €0.04/kWh after 2 600 hours. In 2005, the tariff was again reviewed with Decree-Law n.º 33-A/2005, of February 16 (2005). This time the tariff was reduced to €0.074/kWh, but the guarantee was extended to 15 years. After this period, operators were remunerated to market prices.

The feed-in tariff was an important source of income for small electricity producers. By guaranteeing a fixed price for producing electricity, small producers entered the energy market with less risky investments. Thus, small companies were less likely to be overshadowed by large companies, which had more financial margin to charge cheaper electricity prices and outcompete small producers (Interviewee 4 2023).

«(The tariff) in my opinion, it was something well done by Brussels; because this was entering the market, we were small, and the incumbents would smother us in three strokes. They only needed to offer prices at zero or close for any project that we had to not have profits, and go bankrupt after one or two years. When it was broke, the incumbents would buy it dirt cheap, and everything would be under their hood. That's when the European Union said «no no, these guys, to not be crushed by the incumbents, must have a guaranteed tariff». And that tariff had the State's approval. This was really important for us, because we were suspicious of the banking sector to finance these projects» [interviewee 4]

Indeed, banks initially harboured scepticism towards financing wind energy projects, perceiving them as unconventional industrial investments that lacked traditional elements such as labour and tangible raw materials. The advent of the feed-in tariff conferred a degree of financial autonomy to developers, enabling them to meet their initial investment requirements without resorting to loans. Consequently, the management of WPPs shifted towards smaller, locally rooted companies that were under the ownership umbrella of larger corporate entities (Delicado et al. 2015; Interviewee 5 2023).

The generous feed-in tariff triggered a significant uptick in demand for grid connections to WPPs. In 2003, the first public tender, designed to allocate connection rights to the grid, initiated a public consultation process. However, successive delays led to the tender being cancelled two years later by the new socialist government (Interviewee 4 2023). In 2005, a new public tender for 1800 MW was launched following RCM n.º 169/2005, of October 24 (2005), and Decree-Law n.º 33-A/2005, of February 16 (2005). Phase A of the tender granted 1200 MW and established a feed-in tariff at €0.074/kWh (Ferreira 2011 Dec 2). One of the tender's bidding conditions involved working with local manufacturing companies to establish a domestic industrial cluster. The initiative aimed to create jobs and stimulate local economic development while reducing the installation costs for new wind turbines (Martins et al. 2011; IRENA 2013; Delicado et al. 2015). This tender was won by ENEOP, a consortium of energy companies comprising EDP Renewables, Generg, Enel Green Power SpA, and Enercon GmbH of Germany. The project entailed investments exceeding €1.6 billion for the construction of 48 WPPs and an additional €223 million for wind turbine production. Enercon, the leading industrial partner of the consortium, built in Viana do Castelo its first factory outside of Germany, which became an advanced unit specialised in the production of blades, towers, and electrical generators. This endeavour boosted the share of national inputs from 20% to 100%, accompanied by exports that surpassed 60% of the output in 2011 (Bento and Fontes 2015b). Phase B of the tender granted 400

MW and was secured by the Ventinveste consortium, while phase C granted 200 MW and was distributed among several small projects. No new tenders were opened after this one.

Between 2004 and 2009 Portugal witnessed an annual installation of over 500 MW of wind power annually. At the same time, wind turbine prices were rising everywhere (Figure 3), in spite of the declining cost trajectories predicted by the learning curve theory and observed in the previous decades (Grubler et al., 2012). This reflected a general movement at an international level due to the joint effect of a surge in demand for wind turbines and the raise of production costs motivated by increasing labour, materials prices, and profit margins (Bolinger and Wisser, 2012). Still, the increase in income of electricity generated from wind in Portugal more than offset the increase in costs, ensuring that WPPs continued to be profitable.

4.2.3 INSTALLED WIND CAPACITY

The aforementioned policies collectively spurred a boom of wind energy exploration. Between 2000 and 2004, 61 new WPPs entered into operation, totalling a capacity of 622 MW; and between 2005 and 2009, 134 new WPPs were brought online, contributing to a cumulative capacity of 3 GW. Moreover, wind turbine capacity scaled-up, progressing from the initial deployment of 500 kW turbines in 1996 to the utilisation of 3 MW turbines in 2003.

By 2011, the installed wind energy capacity had reached 4,364 MW, constituting 21% of the total capacity (DGEG, 2013). Consequently, the proportion of wind energy in total electricity consumption rose to 18% in 2012 (DGEG, 2013), making Portugal the second-highest in Europe, surpassed only by Denmark. This significant contribution was pivotal in elevating the share of renewable energies in final electricity consumption, from 21.1% in 1999 to an impressive 45.3% in 2011, which is also one of the highest in Europe (Figure 1).

The surge in renewable energy investment catapulted Portugal to the third position in Europe, with 46.7% of energy production originating from renewables by the end of this phase. In less than a decade, Portugal increased nearly 20% the penetration of renewable energy in its electric system (Delicado et al. 2015). In fact, while in 2004 wind power generation reached 500 MW, ten years later it had soared to nearly 5 GW, a tenfold increase in capacity.

The market share of wind energy in Portugal can be characterised as an oligopoly, with a substantial concentration of economic investments (and revenues) among five different companies — EDP Renewables, Iberwind, New Finerge, Trustwind and Generg — collectively controlling more than 60% of the market. This high economic and financial concentration underscores the dominance of these entities in the wind energy sector.

4.2.4 FINANCIAL SHARING

Decree-Law 339-C/2001 additionally mandated that companies operating wind parks were obligated to pay municipalities a rent equivalent to 2.5% of the monthly payment received by the energy receptor. This policy served two goals: firstly, to ensure compensation for local communities affected by the impacts of wind energy installations, and secondly, to mitigate local resistance to WPP construction by legitimising their development (Bento and Fontes 2015a; Interviewee 5 2023). The policy proved highly effective in achieving these goals. Many WPPs were situated in rural or underdeveloped areas, and this source of income was substantial for those municipalities (Delicado et al. 2015), which led to numerous local mayors consequently endorsing these projects. However, it's

worth noting the policy was occasionally utilised as a form of “virtue signalling” by project developers to avoid further engagement with, or provision of, additional benefits to local communities (Delicado et al. 2015). Indeed, no cases were found in the NCRP where communities benefited from WPPs other than the monthly payment mandated by this policy. Nonetheless, it did succeed in diminishing opposition, as there are few documented cases of resistance to WPP deployments in the NCRP from local communities (Delicado et al. 2015).

An additional factor contributing to the decline in local opposition was the rent provided to landowners for hosting wind turbines. The majority of non-protected land in Portugal is privately owned, especially in the mountainous areas of the NCRP, where lands were not highly productive and held limited financial value. Wind turbines presented an appealing financial opportunity for landowners, allowing them to lease their lands for hosting turbines and turn those lands into profitable assets (Interviewee 6 2023).

«What we observed is that, during public consultations, those in favour of the wind power plants were usually the landowners where they were going to be installed. In Portugal property is divided into very small parcels, thus what happened was almost a lottery: if the company decided to place a turbine in a land, the impacts of that land were not just felt by its landowner, but also by those around it. What people sometimes rebelled against was they had all the prejudice of noise, vibrations, all those things, and none of the benefits, because formally the turbines were in the neighbours' land» (Interviewee 5 2023)

4.2.5 PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

Public opinion on WPPs has been notably varied and not uniformly clear. Some citizens have expressed concerns regarding issues such as noise and safety. For example, in Torres Vedras, local residents created a petition against a WPP because the turbines were proposed to be placed within 250 m of houses, in contrast to the recommended 300 m by the Regional Commission (Lusa 2009 Apr 20). Some individuals have shown appreciation for the turbines, sometimes lining up to get a closer look. Another challenge encountered during this phase was that public consultation processes, mandated by law, were either not effectively disseminated or were communicated close to the deadline. As a result, citizens desiring to voice their opinions often had limited opportunities to do so through formal participation channels (Delicado et al. 2015).

During the phase of upscaling and growth, environmental non-governmental organisations (ENGOS) played a significant role in challenging wind energy projects. Quercus emerged the most active ENGO in the opposition to WPPs (Interviewee 1 2023), followed by the League for Nature Protection (LPN, Liga para a Proteção da Natureza) and the Portuguese Society for the Study of Birds (SPEA, Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves).

The primary reasons for opposing WPPs in the NCRP have mostly revolved around environmental impacts. For example, parks in the northeast (e.g. Lameira, Douro Sul) faced criticism for their potential impacts on the populations of the Iberian Wolf (*Canis lupus signatus*), a species with an important conservation status (classified as Endangered, protected under the Habitats Directive and national law). Other reasons include the impact on bat and bird populations (e.g. in Serra da Estrela), as well as concerns about the power plants' location within or near protected areas or regions with high natural and cultural heritage values.

Box 1 – Serra da Freita

The Serra da Freita WPP, with 16 turbines and a 36,8 MW capacity, is integrated within a Natura 2000 Network site, called Serras da Freita e Arada. The location is also protected under the Habitats Directive and is part of a mountain range important for the conservation of the Iberian Wolf.

The public consultation got three statements: two from local ENGOS — Urtiarda, and the Association for the Defense of Arouquense Heritage (Associação de Defesa do Património Arouquensa), which was subscribed by 75 citizens — and one local citizen. Both ENGOS expressed their opposition to the project, highlighting the strong impact on the natural landscape, its location within a protected area, and knowledge gaps in the environmental impact assessment. The associations also highlighted the lack of available information about the project, raising concerns about the prioritisation of economic interests over local benefits. The local citizens questioned the economic viability of the project.

The project underwent scrutiny in municipal assembly meetings, where concerns were raised regarding its location and the financial transactions involving the executive body. Local communities also sought clarification on how the project's profits would be used. Some residents expected a reduction in their electricity bill when the park became operational, a prospect that did not materialise. Noise emerged as a notable concern for inhabitants in nearby parishes. Additionally, one conspicuous adverse impact was the establishment of pathways leading to the turbines. This development not only increased accessibility to previously remote and pristine areas but also attracted a surge in tourist activity, with individuals utilising these pathways extensively to closely observe the turbines (Delicado et al. 2015).

Nevertheless, the WPP of Serra da Freita was mostly accepted by the local residents, and is now part of the landscape of Arouca. There were some concerns raised by local associations and some residents, but no major backlash was observed, and the residents ended conforming with the park after it became fully operational.

4.3 PHASE OF STAGNATION (2012–2020)

Since 2011, the expansion of wind development that characterised the previous decade has stagnated, with fewer than 10 WPPs being constructed annually. This slowdown can be attributed to a combination of three key factors: (1) the economic crisis of 2008; (2) a government change in 2011; (3) limited availability of optimal locations for new wind parks.

4.3.1 ECONOMIC CRISIS

In mid-2011, the Portuguese economy came under close examination by the International Monetary Fund, the European Central Bank, and the European Commission. Subsequently, the prime minister at the time requested a bailout from the European Union after his resignation was prompted by the rejection of the State Budget by opposing parties in Parliament. Following the bailout, national

elections were organised, and the government changed from the Socialists to the coalition between the Social Democrats and the People's Party.

Since 2012, there has been significant regulatory instability in the Portuguese wind energy market. Decree-Law n.º 25/2012, of February 6 (2012), was arguably the first moment that signalled a shift in renewable energy development, including wind energy. The government suspended all new power generation allocation procedures indefinitely, a move criticised by many associations and organisations, such as APREN.

Meanwhile, the Memorandum of Understanding that ruled the conditions for the financial assistance to Portugal defined specific measures for the energy sector (IRENA 2013). The feed-in tariffs were the main target of the Special Regime. Notably, the regime called for a review of support schemes for renewable energy production and mandated the renegotiation of existing contracts to achieve a lower feed-in tariff. For new contracts in the renewables sector, there was an expectation to revise the feed-in tariff downward, preferably through a digressive tariff, ensuring that compensation did not excessively cover the costs of maintaining WPPs. Consequently, the feed-in tariff stopped being applied to renewable energy installations after November 2012, when Decree-Law n.º 215-B/2012, of October 8 (2012) came into force. This decree-law revoked all previous legislation that defined a feed-in tariff, although previous WPPs maintained their contracted tariff at the time. Two new remuneration options emerged: (1) the general regime, where energy was sold at market price or through bilateral agreements; (2) feed-in tariffs defined in a public tender. However, the second option was never put into practice as no new tenders were opened for the wind energy sector at the time.

These policy changes induced a sense of insecurity in wind energy development in Portugal that led many companies to rethink their investments (Interviewee 8 2023). Furthermore, due to the frenzied development in the preceding period, fewer locations were now available for project developers to pursue profitable wind energy projects. Coupled with the aforementioned economic crisis, this resulted in an unfavourable investment scenario for wind energy.

From 2012 onwards, less than 10 WPPs were built every year, a sharp decline from more than 30 power plants being built each year at the peak of the previous phase. In fact, in 2017, it marked the first year since 1998 in which no new wind energy projects were developed at all.

4.3.2 OTHER EVENTS

Another problem that rose in this phase, and still persists today, was the lengthy approval processes for WPPs. Staff shortages, dysfunctional organisation, and unclear legislation led to permits sometimes taking *years* until finally getting approval by the General Direction of Energy and Geology (Direção Geral de Energia e Geologia, DGEG). This unpredictability dissuaded many project developers from pursuing wind energy projects in the country due to the heightened risk of losing their investment (see Box 4 for an example).

Interviewee 4 also claimed that many permits were intentionally delayed by staff who did not want to deal with the project.

«The mentality of many of these people, either in APA (Portuguese Environmental Agency) or DGE (former DGEG), but more in APA than DGE, was to say 'look, the Secretary of State is there for two years, then, when it leaves, the problems are upon

me. Thus, like this, I put the process in the drawer, wait for the Secretary to leave, and for the developer to give up'. That was their mentality» (Interviewee 4 2023)

Despite the stagnation experienced in this decade, renewable energy production in Portugal has achieved noteworthy records, largely attributable to the frenzied development of the previous decade. For example, in May 2016, Portugal reached an incredible milestone of running on renewable energy alone for four days straight (Neslen 2016 May 18). In this period, wind provided 22% of electricity generation, and renewable sources collectively provided nearly 50%. Despite the slower development of renewable energy in the last years — only 550 MW of wind capacity were added between 2013 and 2016 — the proliferation of turbines in the growth and up-scaling phase prompted this record, a feat only surpassed by Denmark at the time.

As the first WPPs reached the end of their life-cycle, the government issued Decree-Law n.º 94/2014, of June 24 (2014). This was the first policy mentioning WPP repowering, and issued different regimes between the initial plant and the repowered plant. The feed-in tariff for the repowered turbines was fixed to €0.060/kWh.

Box 2 – Serra do Marão

Serra do Marão is one of the highest mountains in northern Portugal. It is characterised by a notable richness of quartz stones and hosts a diverse array of animal species such as the Iberian wolf, the imperial eagle and the chough. It is part of Douro Vinhateiro, which was classified by UNESCO as a World Heritage Site in 2001. Despite its protected status, that has not stopped WPPs (e.g. Penedo Ruivo) from being installed in Marão during the upscaling and growth phase. Presently, the mountain accommodates 60 wind turbines.

In 2018, a new wind park was announced for Serra do Marão by a local promoter named “PAREM – Parque Eólico do Marão, Lda.”. Following the mandatory Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), a 30-day public consultation was opened, during which several entities and associations and two citizens submitted their statements. The citizens and associations dedicated to environmental conservation, encompassing geological and biological aspects, were the only opposing voices against the project. The Geological Society of Portugal opposed the project due to the irreversible impacts that turbines would inflict on a unique quartzitic formation hardly found elsewhere in Iberia. ZERO, Quercus, and the two citizens also expressed concerns about the project, citing a lack of viable alternatives and knowledge gaps within the EIA, potential impacts on bats, the imperial eagle, and the Iberian wolf, as well as the project’s placement in an area within the Natura 2000 network area (PTCON0003) and an Important Bird Area (PT049). Although the project details were not widely disseminated at first, Quercus garnered public attention to the project with a statement in May 2019, during the ongoing public consultation. They declared their intention to file a court action against the project to UNESCO, which was picked up by many national newspapers.

In September 2019, the Portuguese Environmental Agency issued an unfavourable decision to the project. While it did not initially draw significant attention from local communities, the statements of ENGOs and the looming threat of legal action played a decisive role in haltering the construction of the wind park.

Later in 2021, the same developer submitted a revised version of the same project, featuring fewer turbines and located in slightly different locations. However, the Assessment Commission once again issued an unfavourable decision, arguing the new project did not address the issues stated in the previous project, despite the reduction in the number of turbines.

4.3.3 WINDFLOAT ATLANTIC

Despite this phase being marked by a stagnation of onshore wind development, a remarkable event of international importance occurred at the beginning and the end of this phase: the WindFloat project. The uniqueness of the project and the public involvement in it merit a dedicated subsection.

In 2011, WindFloat 1, a project promoted by EDP, became operational. WindFloat 1 marked the first floating offshore wind turbine in the world using a semi-submersible structure to support a multi-megawatt wind turbine rather than the traditional piles fixed on the ocean floor. It was installed on the Portuguese coast, near Aguçadoura (Viana do Castelo), and it was connected to the grid at the end of December 2011. The WindFloat 1 project involved the development and construction of a demonstration unit, using a 2 MW commercial turbine. The turbine operated for five years with high availability, producing more than 17 GWh, in a sea with waves of more than 7 m and remained operational even in the face of waves reaching 17 m.

With the success of floating offshore wind turbines demonstrated, EDP moved on to create WindFloat Atlantic, the first floating wind power plant in continental Europe, using the same floating technology described previously (EDP 2020). The project totalled an investment of €125 million from the European Investment Bank, the EU program, NER300, and the Portuguese government through the Portuguese Carbon Fund, to support the development of this pioneering technology. Furthermore, the WPP received a feed-in tariff of €0.10/kWh that will last for 25 years. The wind park consists of three turbines mounted on floating platforms, securely anchored to the seabed, boasting a total installed capacity of 25 MW. Located 20 km off the coastline of Viana do Castelo, this innovative project showcased the potential of floating offshore wind technology.

The innovation of the project led to its dissemination through international media and forums, and it became a leading example used by the Portuguese government to promote its ambitious renewable energy targets for 2030 (see next phase).

However, the community that was not enthusiastic about WindFloat Atlantic was the fishing sector. The installation of WindFloat Atlantic was expected to reduce the available fishing area and the fishermen requested compensation. Over the following months, a series of meetings and negotiations took place involving representatives from the fishing communities of Viana do Castelo and Caminha, the mayor of Viana do Castelo, the Secretary of State for Fishing, the Minister of Sea, REN, and EDP Renewables. Initially, shipowners agreed to receive €1.2 million, paid by EDP Renewables and REN, for the impacts caused by the WPP (Brito 2023 Jun 8). However, REN imposed a restriction on fishing within 500 m around the submarine cable transporting electricity from the power plant to the grid in Viana do Castelo. Local fishermen, the most affected sector by this restriction, felt aggrieved and began demanding justice. They called for social compensation and threatened to cancel the traditional maritime procession of the Nossa Senhora da Agonia celebration if their concerns were not addressed. Subsequent negotiations took place, leading to the local fishermen ultimately receiving €500,000, again paid by EDP and REN (Brito 2019 Aug 19). Coastal fishermen felt further aggrieved by not receiving compensation for the submarine cable. In protest, they used their vessels to block the path of a ship installing the submarine cable. It remains unclear if they eventually received compensation. Nonetheless, after these events, the construction of the offshore WPP finally commenced.

4.3.4 ENTERING A NEW PHASE

In 2019, Portugal became the 7th country within the EU with the highest share of renewable energy sources. Renewable energies accounted for 53.8% of electricity generation, a remarkable increase from 37.6% in 2009, and covered 30.6% of gross final energy demand, both driven primarily by hydropower and wind generation (Observatório da Energia et al. 2023). This translated into savings of 2,914 million euros (38.6% less) spent in energy imports in the last 10 years, and a slight decline of Portugal's external energy dependency from 81.2% in 2009 to 74.2%, which is still heavily dependent on coal imports.

In 2018, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council (2018) entered into force. The regulation mandated state members to elaborate a national plan for energy and climate and define national targets and policies to reach the EU's goals for 2030 regarding renewable energy. This triggered a new wave of regulatory frameworks that shaped the trajectory of national renewable energy initiatives, including wind energy. The first policy that partially transposed this regulation was the Roadmap for Carbon Neutrality (RCM n.º 107/2019, of July 1 2019). Within this roadmap, the government established objectives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions until 2050,

including a commitment to decarbonise electricity production that included a progressive phase out of coal until 2030.

Following these advancements and the renewed interest of the EU and Portugal to increase renewable energy generation, a new phase of wind energy growth has formed.

4.4 PHASE OF OFFSHORE WIND AND REPOWERING (2020–)

4.4.1 LEGISLATION AND POLICY

The beginning of this phase is marked by the release of the National Energy and Climate Plan (Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima, NECP) (RCM n.º 53/2020, of July 10 2020). The plan followed Regulation 2018/1999 (2018) and the previously mentioned Roadmap for Carbon Neutrality, and serves as the main political instrument for climate and energy policy coordination for the period 2021-2030. The outlined targets include a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 45–55%, an increase in renewable electricity production to 80%, an increase in renewable energy consumption to 47%, a reduction in primary energy consumption to 35%, and a reduction in energy dependency to 65%. To achieve a higher share of renewable energy consumption, the government is prioritising the development of solar energy (aiming for 27% of the national power output by 2030) and, to a lesser extent, wind energy (aiming for 31% of national power output by 2030). The latter increase in capacity will be realised through hybridization (mixing solar with wind), repowering and overpowering (definitions below). Moreover, the plan introduces offshore wind for the first time, with the goal of attracting national and international investors to capitalise on the success of Windfloat Atlantic. The plan has set a target to install 2 GW of offshore wind energy until 2030.

The NECP was a pioneer in the creation of new policies with the goal to accelerate renewable energy production. For example, Decree-Law n.º 30-A/2022, of April 18 (2022), allowed WPPs to inject all electricity produced into the grid without limit to ensure their total capacity was used. Additionally, developers planning to construct new large WPPs (>20 MW capacity or >10 turbines) are required to submit proposals that actively involve local communities in the project. The effects of this participation have yet to be seen. There is also Decree-Law n.º 11/2023, of February 10 (2023), which aimed to simplify environmental impact assessment procedures. While this policy faced significant opposition from environmental organisations for reasons beyond the scope of this discussion, specifically in the context of wind energy, it eliminated the need for an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for single turbines and expanded the range of new WPPs and equipment cases where an EIA is not mandatory.

The need to increase renewable energy production was reinforced after the Russian invasion of Ukraine. To decrease its dependence on oil and gas from Russia, the EU launched the REPowerEU Plan (2022) in May 2022. The goal is to empower the industry to enhance wind and solar energy production to reach the EU's binding target for 2030 to 42.5%, thus nearly doubling the current share of renewable energy in the EU. Member states should add a chapter to their Recovery and Resilience Plan about how they will spend the funds from REPowerEU.

4.4.2 ONSHORE WIND

The current installed capacity of onshore wind in Portugal is 5.7 GW (INEGI and APREN 2023). The NECP 2030, currently under revision with its publication expected to occur soon, foresees a wind

generating capacity of 6.7 GW and 9.0 GW of onshore wind in 2025 and 2030, respectively. The investments predicted for onshore wind energy amount to €4.5 billion to install the targeted 3.4 GW of wind capacity until 2030 (Negócios com sol e vento 2023). The optimal places for wind energy have already been taken in the NCRP, thus few new WPPs are expected. Instead, the expectation is that a large part of this investment and growth in capacity will be used for **repowering** and **overpowering** the existing wind parks.

Repowering involves replacing either partially or entirely outdated turbines of a WPP with newer and technologically more advanced turbines, while overpowering entails adding new turbines to an existing wind park. The distinction between both methods is important. Existing power plants allow an increase of capacity up to 20%, regardless of the method used (Decree-Law n.º 225/2007, of May 31 2007 for overpowering; Decree-Law n.º 15/2022, of January 14 2022 for repowering). But the applied tariffs and environmental impacts are substantially different. Electricity produced by new turbines in overpowering are subject to Decree-Law n.º 94/2014 (2014) and subsequent ordinances, while repowered parks are subject to Decree-Law n.º 15/2022 (2022), where the produced electricity is remunerated to market prices. Overpowering necessitates a new environmental impact assessment due to the exploration of new areas, leading to an increased number of impacts on biodiversity and the landscape. Consequently, overpowering is a more contentious method among environmental organisations. In contrast, repowering typically results in a reduction in the number of turbines. This is because modern turbines available on the market are more powerful and efficient than those built 20 years ago, while the grid capacity has remained unchanged. Thus, to stay within the grid capacity limit (and the 20% increase in capacity imposed by law), some turbines will be decommissioned when repowering a WPP. This reduction mitigates visual and environmental impacts while enhancing energy capacity. Repowering is therefore widely supported by environmental and local associations (Interviewee 1 2023; Interviewee 2 2023).

«Meanwhile, in onshore, the projects that have existed are repowering projects, thus to increase capacity, whose impact is relatively reduced in terms of nature conservation, thus they have not raised such an intense participation from us. In fact, they have raised the opposite position: we actively support repowering, to use areas that were already used for wind energy, and therefore we have clearly positioned ourselves in the direction to even accelerate this process at the same time.» — ZERO speaker

Companies are currently investing in overpowering for more recent WPPs and awaiting older power plants to reach their life expectancy until deciding whether to repower or decommission those plants. For example, EDP Renewables is planning to increase 350 MW of wind capacity until 2026, but the bulk of their investment in wind energy growth will go towards repowering their existing parks after 2026, when many of them will reach their life expectancy (Interviewee 8 2023).

4.4.3 OFFSHORE WIND

Aligned with the ambitions of the EU to accelerate renewable energy development, the Portuguese government announced it would hold its first offshore wind tender in 2022. However, in June of the same year, the Minister for Environment and Climate Action postponed the tender to the next year, and announced it would auction a wind capacity of 6–8 GW. Later, in September, the minister raised the auction to 10 GW, an ambitious proposal that drew international attention (Reuters 2022 Sep 21). For context, the current onshore wind capacity is 5.7 GW (INEGI and APREN 2023). The tender for offshore wind was scheduled to open at the end of 2023 (the last wind energy tender was opened for

onshore wind energy projects in 2005) and attract investments nearing €40 billion. The government created a working group in 2022 to formulate a strategic plan for offshore wind deployments that included LNEG and APREN. They identified five core areas for offshore wind deployment, and suggested a phased approach to the tender. The first phase will allocate 3.5 GW of capacity in the regions with higher wind potential along the north shore, namely Viana do Castelo, Leixões and Figueira da Foz, while subsequent phases will address areas to the south (Brito 2023 Jun 1). Companies such as Iberblue Wind and BayWa have already expressed an interest in exploring offshore wind energy potential in the coast of Viana do Castelo.

The primary source of opposition to date has emanated from the fishing community, echoing the challenges witnessed during the WindFloat Atlantic project. A crucial point of contention revolves around the prohibition of fishing activities near offshore WPPs. The occupation of maritime areas by these infrastructures, coupled with the exclusion zones where fishing will be prohibited, implies that larger fishing vessels will no longer be viable in these waters. Consequently, fishermen anticipate heightened competition for traditional fishing for space. Fishermen associations in Viana do Castelo, Caminha, and Figueira da Foz expressed particular concern regarding the potential impact of the power plants on the migratory patterns of species such as salmon, sable, and lamprey. In response to these worries, fishermen have advocated for the inclusion of compensatory measures for the damages caused by future WPPs in the contractual agreements (Brito 2023 Jun 8).

Fishermen have no knowledge of any analysis done on WindFloat about the long-term impact of the infrastructure on fish populations.

«When WindFloat is active, outside shellfish, there is nothing. When the turbines stop for a week, the fish start to return» — António Coimbra, to the newspaper PÚBLICO

Likewise, scientists have called for more studies about the impacts caused by offshore wind turbines that can complement project specific environmental impact assessments (Rações 2023 Mar 30). Operational wind turbines can lead to habitat loss, function as barriers to migratory routes, and pose risks of bird mortality due to direct collisions. Such risks need to be cautioned, especially considering that floating offshore wind turbines are still a novel technology.

Fishermen were not included in the consultation process for feedback on the offshore wind areas; instead, they were invited to meetings after the areas had already been designated in the Strategic Environmental Assessment and the Allocation Plan for the Exploration of Renewables (PAER, Plano de Afetação de Exploração de Renováveis) (Brito 2023 Jun 8). The timing and scheduling of these meetings, whether in response to fishermen's requests for compensation or at another point, remain unclear. In contrast, environmental non-governmental organisations (ENGOS) acknowledge the consideration given to fishermen but express that they have not been invited to participate in any plans related to offshore wind, including the APER and the Strategic Environmental Assessment (Interviewee 2 2023).

Box 3 – Offshore wind tender consultation

After the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action announced the plan to build 10 GW of offshore wind capacity in Portugal, of which 6 GW will be placed in the north-central region of Portugal, environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs) started to coordinate their action and monitor the plan's progress. Noticeable NGOs that got involved so far are ZERO, focused on sustainability; SPEA, focused on bird conservation; AMP/WWF, focused on animal conservation; and SCIAENA, focused on marine protection.

Government authorities created a working group that was more focused on the economic and energetic components of the offshore wind plan. NGOs, as well as the Institute for Nature Conservation and Forests (public authority for nature conservation), were not involved in the process or called for meetings. NGOs criticised this lack of engagement from government authorities, and ZERO even called for a press conference to denounce the situation.

The four NGOs have only been allowed at the time of writing to participate formally in the public participation process, which occurred between January 30 and March 10. They also invited other smaller NGOs to write a joint statement in the process. The document prepared by NGOs ended up having nearly 20 pages with recommendations on how to combine offshore wind development with environmental protection, including prohibiting all development within Marine Protected Areas and Natura 2000 areas. Indeed, the government later changed the plan to accommodate this recommendation (Green Savers and Lusa 2023 Jul 17).

4.4.4 PUBLIC RESISTANCE

In contrast to the growth phase of onshore wind energy, there is now increased resistance from local communities towards mega projects such as those planned for offshore wind. As previously mentioned, the fast growth of onshore wind energy caught many local communities unaware of the various impacts, both positive and negative, on their territories. Today, there is more available knowledge available and more examples to draw lessons from, meaning impacts derived from wind energy projects can be more easily predicted. Moreover, forms of resistance have become more organised as associations collaborated with each other to improve their resistance strategies. Consequently, citizens have become more proactive in voicing their concerns through frequent and organised protests. While the primary focus has been on large solar power plants, wind energy projects have not escaped this scrutiny. As a result, the government may encounter more significant obstacles in achieving the proposed targets this time.

Box 4 – Mirandela

In phase C of the public tender that occurred in 2005, one of the winning projects aimed to build a wind park in Mirandela, situated in the hills of Santa Comba and Passos. In a rare event in Portugal, the winning company Perform3 – owned by Enervento – decided to create a fund, with an initial value of €1 million, to support residents interested in investing in renewable energy (Lusa 2010 Oct 11). This initiative was undertaken in addition to the 2.5% rent that companies owe to municipalities.

Unfortunately the power plant construction was delayed for 14 years due to successive setbacks. Initially, the licence was only issued in December 2019. A new round of negotiations took place between Perform3 and the municipality during the COVID-19 pandemic. While construction works were intended to start in 2022, they had to be postponed to avoid interfering with the Iberian wolf breeding season (Brito 2022 Aug 6).

Around the same time, a group of citizens, mostly academics, started to mobilise against the park. The reason was the cave paintings that would be irreversibly impacted by the wind park. The cave paintings dated back to the Neolithic age, 7,000 years ago, drawn by the first agro-pastoral societies of the post-glacial period. It is the most diverse and dense concentration of schematic figures in Portugal, only comparable to Las Batuecas, south of Salamanca. In fact, the close proximity of both locations has led to the idea of a joint application as an UNESCO Cultural Heritage site, something that would be threatened if the wind park ever got built.

The citizen/academic movement, called «Together for the Hill of Passos free of windmills!» (“Juntos pela serra de Passos sem ventoinhas!”) launched a petition to stop the park, highlighting the enormous natural and cultural value of the area. This led to two municipal deputies calling for a protective order to stop the park until archeological studies were done. The coordinator of UNESCO itself got involved by sending a letter to the President of the Republican Assembly asking not to hasten the park’s licensing, and to involve the local communities and the appropriate entities to structure a joint management plan for the territory. The project developer, with the support of the mayor of Mirandela, reaffirmed its intention to advance with the construction despite the opposition, but was again stopped by the Minister of Culture in December 2022, who demanded that an archeological evaluation of the site be conducted before. Other parties such as the leftist Bloco de Esquerda took an interest in the case.

The citizen movement finally advanced with an application to classify the area as a Site of Public Interest. If successful, this would effectively stop the park from being constructed. This led the Public Ministry to install a judicial order in April 2023 against the park, effectively stopping it until a judge passes the sentence.

4.5 TIMELINE

Figure 7. Timeline of wind energy development within the north-central region of Portugal between the years of 1985 and 2023.

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

What have been key instances, events and phases?

The history of wind development in Portugal can be split into four distinctive phases, each with a significant difference in wind energy growth rate and focus.

The formative phase marked an interest of national stakeholders to explore wind energy for scientific and commercial purposes. The first wind power plants (WPPs) were built after 1985, and the first feed-in tariff for wind energy was enacted in 1988. Works were also underway to develop a national map of wind energy potential, whose first version was released in 2000. During this time, investments were risky, and stakeholders mostly observed what was happening in other countries and how the technology was maturing. This resulted in a slow but steady growth of wind capacity.

The growth and upscaling phase was marked by new and attractive financial incentives that provided increased security for project developers aiming to invest in wind energy. Wind turbines were now more profitable thanks to scientific and technological advancements that led to an increase in their capacity. The public tender organised by the government in 2005 led to the creation of an industrial cluster that improved national production of wind energy. All these events resulted in an exponential increase of wind capacity in the north-central region of Portugal (NCRP) that led the country to surpass other EU members in achieving its renewable energy targets.

Around 2010, amid the peak of the economic crisis, wind energy in Portugal approached a plateau. Profitable locations for installing WPPs became scarce, inducing escalating uncertainty for project developers. In 2012, a new governing coalition came into power and enacted a law (Decree-Law n.º 25/2012) that suspended the attribution of new connection points to the public electricity grid. Together with the economic crisis, these events marked a phase of stagnation for wind energy development in Portugal. Throughout this phase, the annual count of new wind parks dwindled to fewer than 10, a substantial contrast from the preceding phase's peak of over 30 annually.

In 2020, a renewed commitment to renewable energy development emerged with the publication of the National Energy and Climate Plan. This set the stage for a series of policies geared towards augmenting renewable energy production, featuring increasingly ambitious targets for 2030. The expansion and repowering of existing onshore WPPs are expected to contribute significantly to capacity increases. However, the central focus of the government now lies on offshore wind. After the success of WindFloat Atlantic, the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action announced a goal to install a capacity of 10 GW of offshore wind by 2030 and outlined plans to conduct a new public tender. The tender will be phased, with the initial phase concentrating on offshore wind areas in the north (Viana do Castelo) and centre (Figueira da Foz) of the country, where wind potential is most pronounced.

What have been key actors (and coalitions of actors) and their activities? I.e. actors are human and more than human actors.

The formative phase of wind energy in Portugal saw key participation from researchers, project developers, and government authorities, and the renewable energy association APREN. Their collaborative effort led to policies that created attractive investments in wind energy initiatives. The wind map and atlas developed by LNEG in the early 2000s, EOLOS, highlighted the vast wind potential in the NCRP. Coupled with attractive feed-in tariffs and public tenders, project developers raced to

identify optimal locations for wind power plants (WPPs), ultimately leading to a near saturation of onshore wind energy in these regions.

During this phase, the central role played by researchers shifted, with municipalities emerging as key participants after wind technology matured. Municipalities began actively promoting wind energy projects in their territory to profit from the 2.5% rent mandated by law, a substantial financial incentive considering many of these municipalities were located in rural areas.

Simultaneously, environmental non-governmental organisations (ENGOS) initiated opposition to WPPs that compromised the natural and cultural landscape's value. However, this opposition was restrained when contrasted with trends in other European countries. Citizen engagement with wind energy projects was also minimal during this period. Local discontent with WPPs surfaced only after they entered operation, indicating a lack of awareness among local communities regarding the impacts associated with these projects.

What have been relevant legal and regulatory changes?

Feed-in tariffs were perhaps the most determinant mechanism that influenced wind energy growth in Portugal. The first feed-in tariff was enacted by Decree-Law nº 189/88. It was one of the first feed-in tariffs implemented in Europe, but was not very successful in accelerating wind energy development. Decree-Law 339-C/2001 and Decree-Law nº 33-A/2005 provided more generous feed-in tariffs for wind energy producers and were responsible for much of the wind energy growth that occurred in the up-scaling and growth phase. When Decree-Law nº 215-B/2012 was enacted, ending all feed-in tariffs for new WPPs, the number of new WPPs tumbled.

While feed-in tariffs incentivized investments by project developers, European policies dictated the pace of national wind energy development. For example, Directive 2001/77/EC required member states to define ambitious renewable energy targets by 2010. Portugal abided by setting a wind energy capacity target of 3.75 GW by 2010, which impelled all major policies enacted in that decade to accelerate wind energy growth. The same thing occurred with EU Regulation 2018/1999 and REPowerEU, which drove Portugal to look into new ways to expand renewable energy production, particularly repowering WPPs and offshore wind.

What have been relevant changes in narratives/discourses?

Wind energy actors have been aligned in exploiting the national wind energy capacity since the earliest phases, but their approaches differed. For example, ENGOS generally support wind energy projects as long as they don't compromise ecosystem integrity.

The narrative took a relevant turn with the change in the ruling parties in 2011. The new coalition, Portugal À Frente (Portugal Forward), shifted its focus toward improving energy efficiency rather than constructing new power plants, implementing policies that significantly impeded wind energy development.

What role has the notion of energy justice and energy sovereignty played in the development of wind energy? How have these notions been framed and practised?

Portugal has emerged as a frontrunner in the European Union's wind energy sector, primarily attributed to the groundwork laid in the 80s and 90s through dedicated research and exploration. The strategic policies enacted at the turn of the century further solidified Portugal's position, rendering it

an appealing location for secure investments in wind energy by large players in the field of renewable energy. This, in turn, fuelled a substantial expansion of onshore wind energy, to the point of saturating optimal locations. Presently, the country is set to extend its leadership by venturing into offshore wind, as evidenced by recent announcements outlining important initiatives in this domain.

Nevertheless, it can be argued that a substantial portion of this growth occurred due to the limited engagement of the public in wind energy projects. The factors contributing to this phenomenon are not entirely clear but appear to result from a combination of factors: a lack of awareness regarding the impacts associated with WPPs, particularly in the initial phases; insufficient information on how and when citizens can participate in a project; and a prevailing cultural inclination toward low public involvement in societal matters. Indeed, a perpetual cycle seems to have emerged around wind energy projects, where local communities exhibit low levels of participation, those willing to participate are unsure when to do so, and those who know have limited experience engaging with the project, leading to a dearth of tangible results and fostering feelings of helplessness and conformity. Consequently, the absence of community involvement in wind energy projects in the NCRP is unsurprising. All profits from wind energy projects go towards project developers, with the exception of the 2.5% rent due to municipalities and the rent payable to landowners where wind turbines are deployed.

An intriguing observation is the absence of wind energy cooperatives in Portugal. While energy communities, primarily centred around photovoltaic energy production, are beginning to emerge in the NCRP, wind energy cooperatives remain non-existent. The sole energy cooperative in the country, Coopérnico, primarily focuses on solar power, although they have expressed an interest in expanding their portfolio towards wind energy (Interviewee 7 2023). Stakeholders suggest that the dearth of community initiatives in energy is a consequence of insufficient incentives and complex legislation.

Conversely, ENGOs, particularly Quercus, voiced opposition to numerous wind energy projects due to their perceived environmental and landscape impacts. This opposition was expressed through various means, including the publication of blog posts, articles in newspapers, the submission of recommendations during public consultations, and, on occasion, resorting to legal action to halt projects entirely. Quercus, along with other ENGOs, often took a stance either independently or in collaboration with other environmental organisations, and rarely sought local support.

The opposition of fishermen communities to offshore wind was remarkably more fierce. The WindFloat Atlantic project encountered opposition from the fishing sector, concerned about the reduction in fishing areas. It stood out as one of the few projects where a sector received financial compensation for the damages inflicted by a WPP. Now, fishermen communities are advancing with further protests to the offshore wind public tender, threatening to stop their activities if their concerns are not addressed.

Due to limited public participation and the expression of opinions in public consultations, assessing the role of justice in the development of wind energy in the NCRP is challenging. Local residents in the NCRP have largely accepted wind turbines as part of the landscape after a decade of wind turbine proliferation. Social impacts, such as noise, vibrations, and visual disturbances, were rarely mentioned, distinguishing the region from other European areas. The opening of new trails to enhance turbine accessibility was often viewed negatively, as it increased movement and facilitated tourist access to previously pristine and remote areas. The largest disappointment was the expectations of local communities to benefit from reduced electricity bills not being met after WPPs entered into operation. Meanwhile, project developers emphasised the environmental benefits of renewable energy production and the financial benefits for municipalities that accepted their projects. Therefore,

the question remains if the conformity of local communities is due to a feeling of contentment with local wind energy projects, or helplessness for not knowing how they could get involved.

6 SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 SYNTHESIS OF RESULTS

Our research shows that rapid development of wind energy in Portugal was achieved in two steps. First, thanks to an impulse by research centres, who wanted to explore the academic and economic potential of wind energy. Second, by a collaboration between national governments and project developers. Government officials wanted investments in methods that reduced Portugal's dependence on coal imports to produce electricity, and that reduced CO₂ emissions at a time when alerts were being globally disseminated by the scientific community about the causes and impacts of global warming. Project developers were interested in generating more revenue, and took advantage of the financial incentives provided by the government to risk high investments in building onshore WPPs.

Public opposition to onshore wind energy projects in Portugal was low when compared with other European countries. This was another factor that contributed to the rapid development of wind energy. Decree-Law 339-C/2001 ensured that municipalities had a financial compensation from WPPs implemented in their territory, which helped to reduce opposition from municipalities and ensure the money was invested locally. However, many local communities were not informed on where this money was being spent, and many showed disappointment when they realised their expectations to see their electricity bills reduced were not met. With the focus now on repowering currently existing power plants, instead of building new ones, it is unlikely that opposition will pick up for onshore wind.

Conversely, opposition to offshore wind has been fierce since the beginning, particularly from the fishing sector. When WindFloat Atlantic was announced, fishermen demanded compensation for the loss of fishing area caused by the WPP. The protests were successful and the diverse fishing sectors received financial compensations. However, after the announcement of a public tender to distribute offshore WPPs through the west Portuguese coast, fishermen intensified their protests due to the consequent larger loss of fishing area. They threatened to stop their activity if their concerns were not addressed.

It is clear that public participation in wind energy projects has been mostly limited to public entities and project developers, with ENGOs sometimes showing their opposition to certain projects. This means there is much room left for **social innovations** and **participatory practices** in wind energy projects that lead to the creation of local value and ownership. With that in mind, we wrote a list of recommendations to foster a just and effective wind energy governance for the future of wind energy in the NCRP.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

6.2.1 INVITE STAKEHOLDERS TO PARTICIPATE DURING PROJECT DESIGN

To achieve **procedural justice**, it is crucial that governmental authorities and project developers **create a transparent framework where communities and sectors can provide constructive**

feedback before the project is submitted for approval. This will enhance the creation of local value and ensure the project is safeguarded against undetected impacts. For **offshore wind**, this includes calling **ENGOS** to use their knowledge to mitigate ecosystem impacts, the **fishing sector** to negotiate territorial and financial compensations for the loss of fishing areas, and the tourism sector, who has yet to raise its concerns in the NCRP about offshore wind, to discuss solutions to reduce visual impact and the impact on whale watching activities, if applicable. These actors should analyse together the best areas for deploying wind turbines with minimal interference to their activities and values.

6.2.2. ENACT POLICIES THAT SUPPORT PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

Wind power plants in the NCRP are entirely owned by private companies. **To increase the democratisation of energy, it is imperative that national and regional governments enact policies that facilitate cooperative ownership of wind energy projects.**

The ongoing phase of **repowering** power plants presents a valuable opportunity to actively engage with local communities. Soliciting feedback on the renewal of associated infrastructure, including optimal turbine and cable placement, modifications to road accesses, and potential financial investment in the community, can enhance **distributive justice**. An illustrative case in Abruzzo, Italy, highlights the positive outcomes of such community involvement during a WPP repowering project (Maleki-Dizaji and del Bufalo 2019). Through public meetings, the local community provided valuable input to project developers that led to reduced environmental and visual impacts. Subsequently, the creation of new local jobs and the restoration of the road network and grid connections ensured economic benefits to the community. This successful approach not only addressed social concerns but also fostered **greater community acceptance**.

For WPPs that will not be repowered because they are no longer profitable (Interviewee 8 2023), local communities could reach an agreement with companies and municipalities to make a local investment in the repowering process and take total or partial ownership of the WPP. Both situations must be supported with adequate policy that facilitates the participation of citizens and the request of loans, if necessary, to reach a cooperative ownership agreement, and the endorsement of municipalities to facilitate this transition.

Offshore wind provides another timely opportunity to address the historical lack of public participation in wind energy projects. Government authorities should leverage this opportunity to make room for social innovation and citizen participation options through engagement with coastal communities. The offshore wind tender could include specific conditions, mandating that proposals integrate measures for citizen co-ownership of the project. For example, fishing communities could be encouraged to participate in project ownership and work as vigilant observers for turbine operation, notifying project developers whenever action is necessary. This approach not only addresses concerns about the potential loss of fishing areas to offshore WPPs, but also involves fishermen in the project's success by providing them with a share of the income from electricity generation.

6.2.3 REDUCE PERMITTING TIMES

Currently, permitting can take many years from project submission until authorisation by local and governmental authorities. This discourages project developers from investing in national wind energy generation, delays the achievement of renewable energy targets, and increases susceptibility to market and policy changes that may force the project to be altered midway.

To address this challenge, we recommend **modernising the digital infrastructure** that is used for the permitting process. Subsequently, we recommend **hiring and educating more staff** to get familiar with the permitting process and increase digital literacy. For wind energy in particular, staff should be trained in handling repowering and overpowering permits. Finally, it is important to have a **permitting guide** accessible to project developers and public authorities that explains the different steps necessary by each actor from project submission until authorisation. This last recommendation has already been addressed by APREN, who has prepared a permitting guide for renewable energies this year, with participation from APA and DGEG (Oliveira 2023 Sep 15). The guide currently has no information for offshore wind, but this should be incorporated in the next version.

6.2.4 MONITOR THE LONG-TERM IMPACTS OF OFFSHORE WIND

Offshore wind energy and the use of floating platforms to host wind turbines is still a relatively new technology. Therefore, the impacts caused by these structures are currently being studied. The public tender for offshore wind will be done through phases, and in the first phase 3–4 GW of capacity will be auctioned in the NCRP. We recommend using this opportunity to **set up a scientific laboratory to monitor the long-term impacts caused by offshore wind turbines**. These include impacts on bird mortality, bird migratory routes, marine mammal migratory routes, fish diversity and abundance, changes in sediment and water turbidity levels, and noise levels. A similar approach has been done in Catalonia (Spain) recently, where the government advanced with an innovative research infrastructure for offshore wind research located in the Gulf of Roses, called PlemCat (Redacció 2023 Feb 22). A condition in the public tender to equip the power plants with state-of-the-art monitoring technology (e.g. LiDAR) and infrastructure would serve two objectives. First, it would further Portugal's position as an ambitious country that aims to pursue offshore floating wind technology while safeguarding environmental protection in return. Second, it would provide information to improve the WPP designs for the next phases of the public tender.

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ANNEX 1: BIBLIOGRAPHY

All documents consulted were cited in this report.

ANNEX 2: INTERVIEWEES

Interviews	Role	Date	Setting	Duration
Interview 1	Quercus speaker	2023-06-19	Online	00:43
Interview 2	ZERO speakers	2023-05-23	Online	01:15
Interview 3	APREN speaker	2023-05-17	Presential	00:59
Interview 4	APREN former executive	2023-06-21	Online	01:37
Interview 5	ICS researcher	2023-05-04	Online	00:45
Interview 6	LNEG researcher	2023-06-19	Online	01:11
Interview 7	Coopérnico executive coordinator	2023-06-01	Presential	00:50
Interview 8	EDP Renewables executive	2023-07-07	Online	00:57

ANNEX 3: MEETINGS AND EVENTS ATTENDED

Event	Type	Date	Description
Accelerating the energy transition: renewable energy communities	Workshop	2023-05-29	Discussion about renewable energy communities. Five companies presented their experience. Wind energy was not mentioned
Science CHANGing Policy	Conference	2023-06-02	Institutional event where the preliminary results of this report were presented
Frontiers in E3: 9th cE3c Annual Meeting	Conference	2023-09-07	Institutional event where the preliminary results of this report were presented